

ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE ALGORITHMS BASED ON THE COMPLEXITY OF THE FACTORIZATION PROBLEM

Sharopova Muhayyo Mukhtar daughter

Asian International University

Teacher of "General technical sciences" department

mukhayyosharopova4@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10512982>

ANNOTATION

In this article, the concepts of electronic digital signature and the main goals of its use are shown. In addition, the science "Cryptography", which is the basis of electronic signature, and the initial encryption algorithms of this science are given, and examples of them are shown. Electronic digital signature algorithms based on the complexity of the factorization problem

Key words: cryptography, factoring

Enter

Electronic digital signature based on RSA public key encryption algorithm. Each i -user of the system (e_i, d_i) - generates a key pair. For this, by taking sufficiently large p and q -prime numbers (these numbers are kept secret), $n = pq$ -number and the value of the Euler function $\varphi(n) = (p-1)(q-1)$ is calculated (this number is also kept secret). Then, $(e_i, \varphi(n))=1$ the number satisfying the condition, i.e., the number e_i -by the number $\varphi(n)$ -which d_i is prime to the number e_i -is calculated by this $e_i d_i = 1 \pmod{\varphi(n)}$ formula. This $(e_i; d_i)$ - pair e_i is declared as - public key and d_i - secret (private) key.

Then i -user j to -user sends encrypted data with signature as follows:

1. Encryption rule: $M^{e_j} \pmod n = C$, where M - open information, S - encrypted information;
2. Decoding rule: $C^{d_j} \pmod n = M^{e_j d_j} \pmod n = M$;
3. Calculation of ERI: $H(M)^{d_i} \pmod n = P_i$,

where i -the -user's P_i -signature is calculated by M the -data's $H(M)$ -hash function value;

4. Checking the ERI: $(P_i)^{e_i} \pmod n = H(M)^{e_i d_i} \pmod n = H(M)$, if $H(M) = H(M_1)$ (here M_1 - decrypted information), then the electronic document is valid, otherwise it is invalid, because according to the hash function property $M = M_1$, their hash values are also equal.

5. Confidential data transfer protocol:

$$[M \cup H(M)^{d_i}]^{e_j} \bmod n = [M \cup P_i]^{e_j} \bmod n = C;$$

6. Protocol for receiving confidential transmitted information:

$$C^{d_j} \bmod n = [M \cup P_i]^{e_j d_j} \bmod n = M \cup P_i, \text{ preliminary information in general}$$

may have been changed, therefore $C^{d_j} \bmod n = M_1 \cup P_i$ and the resulting hash value is u by signature

this expression $(P_i)^{e_i} \bmod n = H(M)^{e_i d_i} \bmod n = H(M)$, and if the received information has a hash value $H(M_1)$, then $H(M) = H(M_1)$ the electronic document is valid, otherwise, it is fake.

ESIGN digital signature algorithm

ESIGN is an ERI algorithm developed by scientists from Japan (NTT, Japan). The tolerance of this algorithm is determined by the complexity of the factorization problem, such as the RSA algorithm.

In the ESIGN algorithm, a pair of large prime numbers p and q serves as a secret key and is determined by the expression $n = p^2 * q$. The pair (n, k) serves as the public key. Here k is a security parameter.

The formation of ERI according to the ESIGN algorithm and its transmission includes the following sequence of steps:

1) M is a hash function for information:

$$m = H(M); \text{ The value of } m \text{ is in the range from } 0 \text{ to } n-1;$$

2) a random number x smaller than $p*q$ is generated;

3) a very small integer w is:

$$w \equiv ((m - x^k) \bmod n) / p * q;$$

4) ERI S is formed for m using the secret key:

$$S \equiv x + ((w / kx^{k-1} \bmod p)) p * q;$$

5) information is transmitted through the communication channel M and ERI S.

Using the received information M and ERI S, the receiving party performs the following sequence of steps:

1) The hash function for M information is $m = H(M)$:

$$\text{calculate } S^k \bmod n \text{ for } S \text{ using public key } (n, k);$$

3) the number a is equal to or greater than the double of the number of bits divided by 3, much smaller than the integer, and 2 is a ;

$$s^k \bmod n \text{ is compared with } m \text{ and } m + 2^a:$$

$$m = s^k \bmod n;$$

$$m + 2^a = s^k \bmod n.$$

If $s^k \pmod n$ is equal to or greater than m and $s^k \pmod n$ is less than $m+2^a$, then ERI is valid, otherwise invalid. The fact that this algorithm has the ability to perform calculations related to x and k in advance makes it possible to speed up the ERI formation process.

This algorithm is much faster than RSA if it uses keys and signatures of the same size, and has the same security as RSA. ESIGN has received a patent in the USA, Canada, England and several countries.

References:

1. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 316-319.
2. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.
3. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
4. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.
5. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.
6. Sharopova, M. (2023). CLASSES AGAIN APPLY. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 106-111.
7. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
8. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
9. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TO'G'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
10. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 66-76.

11. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 383–390.
12. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 391–399.
13. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
14. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
15. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
16. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
17. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
18. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
19. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG–LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
20. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
- 21.
22. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
23. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
24. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.

25. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
26. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 134-139.
27. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
28. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
29. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
30. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
31. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
32. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
33. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
34. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 120-128.
35. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
36. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
37. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.
38. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.

39. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
40. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
41. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
42. Quvvatov, B. U. o'g'li . (2023). ALEXNET - TASVIRLARNI TASNIFLASH UCHUN KONVOLYUTION NEYRON TARMOQ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 77-90.
43. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g'li Quvvatov. (2023). MAXIMUM PRINCIPLE AND ERROR ANALYSIS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 480-486.
44. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
45. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
46. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135-138.
47. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers,2(2), 101-103.
48. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
49. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102-110.
50. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
51. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.
52. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 115-121.
53. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.

54. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420-424.
55. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425-429.
56. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525-532.
57. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
58. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
59. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
60. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
61. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
62. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
63. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
64. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
65. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
66. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.
67. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 35-39.

68. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Hamidov, E. (2023). YADRO ENERGIYASINING XOSSA VA XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182-186.
69. IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION
70. SZ Jurakulov, O Nurboyev - GOLDEN BRAIN, 2023
71. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). FIZIKA FANINI O 'RGANISHNING YUQORI DARAJADAGI STRATEGIYALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
72. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). TA'LIM SOHASIDA FIZIKANING SAN'AT BILAN ALOQALARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
73. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
74. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
75. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
76. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 143-150.
77. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 77-87.
78. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 317-323.
79. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 563-568.
80. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
81. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
82. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.

83. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.
84. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
85. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
86. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
87. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 495-507.
88. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. *Молодой ученый*, (23), 105-106.

